

The Sayings of the Desert Fathers

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Early Christian Monasticism in Egypt, Text, Sayings Text (Greek: Apophthegmata)

The Sayings of the Desert Fathers is attributed to specific monks in the Egyptian and Palestinian deserts. It is an example of ancient literature called apophthegmata, consisting of sayings by and stories about well-regarded figures of wisdom. While the original material was likely passed down orally in Coptic for some time, the oldest written version is in Greek. There are two principal versions of this material organized in different ways. One collection is organized alphabetically according to the names of the monks cited and written about. The other collection is thematic, with sayings and stories organized according to themes such as "Self-Control," "Non-judgment," and "Humility." While the collections abound in overlapping material, the sayings and stories are not entirely identical between the two. While the majority of the monks represented in the text are from the Egyptian regions of Scetis and Nitria in the 4th century C.E., the collection was compiled and redacted in the early 5th century in Palestine. The overwhelming theme of The Sayings of the Desert Fathers is asceticism. The compiler/redactor shaped the material to focus on commonalities in ascetic practice which belie what is now known to be a vast variety of beliefs and practices in Egypt and Palestine.

Date Range: 390 CE - 500 CE

Region: Scetis and the Thebaid, Egypt

Region tags: Egyptian Desert, North Africa, Egypt, Africa

Scetis is modern Wadi Al-Natrun, Egypt, a desert region. The Thebaid borders both the Mediterranean Sea and the Red Sea.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Harmless, William. *Desert Christians: an Introduction to the Literature of Early Monasticism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004. Print.
- Source 2: Chitty, Derwas J. *The Desert a City: An Introduction to the Study of Egyptian and Palestinian Monasticism Under the Christian Empire*. Oxford: Blackwell, 1966. Print.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL:

https://www.academia.edu/7403135/Formation_and_Reformations_of_the_Apophthegmata_Patrum

– Source 1 Description: A good discussion of the historical issues involved in reading, translating, and interpreting the Apophthegmata (Sayings).

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://repository.duke.edu/dc/earlymss/emsgk01100>

– Source 1 Description: Includes two manuscripts of the Apophthegmata Patrum (Sayings of the Desert Fathers), one from the 7th century CE and another from the 14th century CE.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: This collection of sayings and stories advocates explicitly for an ascetic lifestyle as a means of transformation and/or moral perfection.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: This is part of a type of literature known in Greek as Apophthegmata (Sayings). It was meant to collect the wisdom of well-known philosophers or sages for the purpose of moral instruction.

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: It is clear throughout the text that those who are most committed to ascetic living attain the highest levels of authority and are therefore able to teach others.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than

other parts?

– Yes

Notes: One monk says that "the soul prospers in the measure in which the body is weakened."

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: Whether or not the text accurately reflects an overall ideology among different monastic groups, it ultimately seems to show agreement on mind (or soul)- body dualism. Asceticism is said to transform the soul by weakening the influence of the body.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: While there is a great emphasis on the importance of ascetic practice, there is also frequent debate and disagreement in the text on the extent of that practice. Some monks who endanger their lives through excessive fasting or other practices are reprimanded while others are praised for similar practices as they are demonstrating their commitment.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: The text generally spends far more time speaking of Hell than of Heaven. The contemplation of Hell is often used as a contemplative exercise to force monks to be diligent in their asceticism and general spiritual duties and to abandon the passions.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The text spends little to no time on apocalypticism, speaking instead of the afterlife of each individual.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Notes: Corpses are usually buried in accordance with Late Antique Christian custom. However, there is at least one example where a monk does not wish his body to be venerated after death. He orders his disciples to simply drag his body to the mountains and leave it there.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There are several stories in which dead bodies come temporarily to life, usually to provide information only they have. Disembodied spirits of the dead are neither seen nor do they communicate with the living.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Demons are most commonly seen. They are there to tempt the monks or harm them. Angels are also present, often in disguise as humans. Angels usually provide good examples of correct behavior or test the monks on behalf of God.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Again, demons can physically hurt monks while angels in human disguises can be helped by monks. In one story, an angel posing as a handicapped beggar asks a monk for repeated favors such as being carried into town and being bathed, all of which the monk performs without complaint.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Most of both demons' and angels' knowledge is in regard to moral or ethical standards of monks. However, there is no explicit limit set on their knowledge.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Demons are said to occupy the desert, a place where humans are unsafe. In this

sense, monks are viewed as warriors, taking on both the physical dangers of the desert and the demons who dwell there.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

Notes: Again, demons seem to have knowledge of monks' thoughts. Other knowledge isn't relevant to the context of the sayings and stories.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: This seems to be the whole raison d'etre of the demons in this text. They can see and therefore exploit the inner weaknesses of monks.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: Demons can see tendencies in monks and try to exploit the worst ones to make the monks fail at their vocation by giving in to temptations or committing various sins. However, they do not see an irrevocable future. Angels also influence monks' behavior but cannot guarantee that monks will respond appropriately.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Notes: Knowledge beyond what the monks are thinking or doing is irrelevant to the monastic context and thus is not mentioned.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: One monk says that "those who renounce the world but want to keep something for themselves are torn... by the demons who make war on them."

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: Some laypeople are said to be possessed by demons who then speak to monks through their hosts.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The word pantheon would indicate a number of gods. Late Antique Christianity sees its god as the one and only (Trinity notwithstanding). Angels are agents of that god, somewhere between humans and gods and are not gods themselves. Demons, similarly, are agents of the devil who, I suppose could be viewed as a malevolent god but is usually not in the context of Christianity.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text does not guide divination practices as such. However, there is the implication that a life of assiduous asceticism leads one to be able to access knowledge directly from God. this knowledge can concern spiritual things such as biblical interpretation or mundane things, such as the location of water in the desert.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– I don't know

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

Notes: Some ascetic practices, taken to extremes, involve risking one's life. Some sayings or

stories indicate that this is a sign of one's true commitment to God and/or the monastic vocation. Others indicate that this is going too far and that moderation is required.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes

Notes: The Eucharist must be taken regularly, although there is some indication that this can be self-administered in cases where there is no church nearby.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– Yes

Notes: There are very few tales of conversion from any other religion to Christianity. Even these are results of the monk or monks simply providing good examples that so impress the other person that he/she decides on his/her own to convert. There is no extra-Christian proselytizing.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– No

Notes: Antony, the so-called father of Christian monasticism, asks why some are rich and others poor. God answers that Antony should pay attention only to himself because knowing this will not profit him. The indication is that God has ordained the economic order. There are, however, indications that monks were giving to the poor.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Notes: Monks are often punished for hoarding money, possessions, or food.

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Notes: Punishments consist generally of intense, everlasting suffering.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– No

Notes: References to punishment nearly always refer to the afterlife.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: References to rewards are nearly all about the afterlife.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?
– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule
– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions
– No

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: The Messiah's purpose is to be a sacrifice to effect salvation from punishment in the afterlife caused by the dominion of sin.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– I don't know

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– I don't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: While Christianity of this period generally stipulates that one must believe the propositions laid out by the Council of Nicea, there seem to be other answers to how monks can achieve salvation. As usual in this text, there are indications that strict asceticism will save the monk, and even the few laypeople mentioned who practice asceticism.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts
– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities
– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)
– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being
– No

Notes: A caveat: we know that there were differing opinions among early monastics about the nature of the deity. Some clearly thought he was formless so as not to limit him. Others clearly believed he was embodied and anthropomorphic. However, there is very little indication of this debate in this text.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes

- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: This is applied only to monks, not laity.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Monks are generally said to have avoided meat. This has nothing to do with kindness to animals, but rather with the ascetic injunction to avoid luxury.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: Monks often relinquish most of their possessions in the text.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: This is indicated but rarely specified.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: Monks are required to cut off previous social ties including those of family.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Solitary monks are said to perform a variety of prayer practices on their own. There is no universal requirement for such monks who seem to devise these practices on their own. Monks in larger communities follow the prescribed rituals and times.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 5

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

Notes: This text cares far more about orthopraxy than orthodoxy, although there are indication of debates on orthodoxy.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Notes: Each monk is given the title Abba or Apa, the Coptic word for father while nuns are called Amma or mother.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: While formal education is not described extensively in the text, men and women were strictly segregated in separate communities.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Notes: The majority of teacher/disciple relationships are depicted as 1:1 or at most 1:3.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Total obedience to one's teacher is absolutely required.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: There are very few references to specific hierarchical positions. There are, however, superiors mentioned in cenobitic communities.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: Monks are required to participate in whatever form of food production is used. Work is a necessary condition for receiving food from the community. Begging is not permitted.

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: While some monks and monastic communities make use of small scale agriculture, many weave baskets from reeds, selling them either directly to consumers in urban areas or to traders. This money is then used to buy food in the urban areas.

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

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